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UNHUMAN: AN ESSAY ON MONSTROSITY AND THE MONSTER AS A PROMISE OF A POSTHUMAN BEING

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Abstract

To reflect on what a Post/Transhuman is, I will start with the question “*What does it mean to be a human being ?*”³ Then, it will be necessary to first understand what it means to be a human, how it is constituted, and, at what moment it stops being a human and is defined as a non-human less than human or unhuman. It is taken for granted that we all know what it is to be a human. However, in the context of Post-Transhumanist speculation, we would have to go back to the origins to know what we are talking about. In this essay, from a brief tour of Classical Humanism, I will return to the idea of the human that from this vision was gestured as a starting point to re-signify and update the idea of the human in order to know what it means to be a Posthuman. Hence, here I explore that the Humanity and Human are built not only based on what is proper to it, such as being rational, civilized, or possessing free will, among other things; but also on everything it has left behind throughout history and, importantly, for everything that has been left aside: the intolerable, that which is of the order of the monstrous: the unhuman, the inhuman, the radically incomprehensible *Other*.

Hence, this reflection is then based on the understanding of the paradoxical processes involved in the construction of what it means to be Human and from there being able to think about what a Posthuman is. Thus, this work is an initial reflection on the understanding of these processes I’m working on from the model of “*Mobius Strip Topology*”⁴ understanding these as a continuum “*process that can reach change from the human's substrate to Posthuman Terrains*” as proposed in the framework by Sepideh Majidi⁵. Hence, this essay is a continuation of my previous work on my Posthuman Art Residency hosted in the Posthuman Terrains Xenoverse⁶.

³ This question was raised by David Roden in one of the Study Groups from the Posthuman Art and research residency 2022, which I was a part of. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=sOnVKR4s5vU&t=5710s>

⁴ In psychoanalysis, the Mobius strip is a topology used by thinkers like Jacques Lacan to illustrate the paradoxical nature of the psyche, showing how concepts like “inside” and “outside” are not separate but are instead continuous and interconnected, much like the single surface of the strip. It’s a model for understanding how seemingly binary oppositions (e.g., conscious/unconscious, self/other, love/hate) are, in reality, part of a single, continuous loop, where one side is not possible without the other.

⁵ <https://www.posthumanart.com/post/posthuman-terrains-sepideh-majidi> : “*An investigation into the conditions of possibility, not to explain how our reality can change, but how a process I can reach change from the human's substrate*”

Thus, I continue to seek the conditions of possibility to transform the notion of what is understood as being human, instead as an static model, understand it as a transformation process driven to move its borders by surrounding forces and, focusing on how some of this forces acts hidden as a subconscious force that contradicts the very notion of human being as an static entity with unmovable defined boundaries.

For this reflection, I have used the first approach of the Mobius Strip Model as a model that stages paradoxes for the common understanding in representational thinking ,instead of it we have a surface with only one side. As Alireza Taheri propose in his "Psychoanalytic Topology" : *only a paradoxical topology can grasp the object in its inherent contradictions...Lacan's move to topological thinking must be seen as a corrective to both spatial and temporal thought (two aspects of representational thought). An inherent limitation of representational thought is that it depicts contradiction in such a way that "the contradictory is held external to itself, next to and after itself"*⁷.

Then, my lecture here of these subconscious forces is to see it as a continuum but hidden within the twisting of the Mobius strip, which, even though hidden, remains a part of one sided surface, the contradiction is not external to the human identity. Then the human/unhuman are a continuum movement of boundaries. What is hidden in the torsión of the Human Being Moubius Strip? To reflect on this question, I am making here an approach to this Topological Terrain, understanding the hidden forces from authors such W. Benjamin, C.Jung, Julia Kristeva and J. Derrida, searching for the conditions of possibility for the development of a *Posthuman Being*.

Short bio

**Magenta is the artistic name of Maria N. Martínez Bautista, born in México city. She is a Researcher, Transdisciplinary, and Multimedia Designer/Artist in the field of the speculative. She is a Ph.D. candidate in Social Sciences in Communication and Politics and has a master's degree in Sciences and Art for Design (U.A.M.X). Magenta works with digital, analog, and biological media. In her*

to Posthuman Terrains. We are moving from our static models which are determined by the totality of the global structure looking toward new types of models of Posthuman Terrains with the streams of perturbations"

⁶ <https://www.posthumanart.com/posthuman-terrains> , "Odiocia: Transhumanism as an involution" <https://www.posthumanart.com/post/odioica-transhumanism-as-an-involution-by-magenta-1> and in Agency Posthuman lab <https://www.posthumanart.com/posthuman-agency> "Unhuman : The twist in the surface" <https://www.posthumanart.com/post/unhuman> <https://www.posthumanart.com/post/unhuman-the-twist-in-the-surface-by-magenta>

⁷ From : Study Group with Alireza Taheri, "Psychoanalytic Topology":

"Lacanian topology is the contemporary heir to speculative philosophy. The Moebius strip, the Torus, and the Klein bottle all stage paradoxes for the common understanding (e.g. an object that has its centre of gravity outside itself, a surface with only one side). Only a paradoxical topology can grasp the object in its inherent contradictions. Lacan's move to topological thinking must be seen as a corrective to both spatial and temporal thought (two aspects of representational thought). An inherent limitation of representational thought is that it depicts contradiction in such a way that "the contradictory is held external to itself, next to and after itself" (Hegel quoted McGowan, 2019, 118). Time and space are ideological categories insofar as they misrecognize the paradoxical unity of an entity by falsely dividing it into disparate moments. Rather than depict one thing that is internally divided, representational thought puts forward two separate self-identical objects conceived as different only from one another. Lacan's topology corrects this shortcoming and creates a new "imaginary" as an endeavour to overcome the limitations of Kant's transcendental aesthetics" the study group of Lacanian Topology carried out within the activities of the Posthumanart network Residency. [Study Group with Alireza Taheri, "Psychoanalytic Topology"](#)

work she reflects on the unconscious, the irrational, and the future from an approach of critical thinking and philosophical Posthuman theory.

Hence, my reflection begins, on the one hand, by searching in history for what is understood as human and how the development of this concept is not static. One of the hidden forces that bring transformation, moving the boundaries between what is considered human and non-human, is that which is rejected as belonging to the human, external to the human or, in other words *the Other* of human that which is considered an abomination, the monstrous.

**The conditions of possibility are in the past and in the subconscious
(or hidden in the junk room)**

Walter Benjamin proposed revisiting the past to illuminate the present with his analysis of history "*with the brush against the grain*" (Benjamin 1971:81), in this way, redeeming the past itself, recognizing the injustices that go hand in hand with the so-called "progress of humanity". In his thesis, he talks about the political importance that this analysis of "history against the grain" has for the emancipation of the oppressed in the recognition of their particular histories from the past but to be resigned and updated. This is how the oppressed are vindicated in contemporary movements from the story told by those who have been silenced. From this point of view, the future is in emancipation from the past⁸. The future is a continuum from the past. Understanding of time as the spiral in Mobius Strip that returns us the "past".

On the other hand, to be a complete person according to Carl Jung, it is necessary to recognize and integrate one's own shadow (Jung 1939:265), that is, to make conscious what is repressed in the unconscious. The unconscious is not external to our identity. When the opposite happens, what is repressed manifests itself in our frustrations, fears, and insecurities as soon as any confrontation arises between our identification with certain values that culture has imposed on us and what is repressed. If this confrontation is constant and is not resolved, it manifests as disease, hate speeches and myths that justifying it. the monstrosity rises.

So, everything that humanity and humans has hidden, and continues to hide, that which is considered intolerable, that which causes repudiation, horror, and rejection, is the monstrous that threatens the integrity of what is considered human or belongs to human nature. And yet, despite the effort to keep all this in the shadows; there it is, dormant. It is a hidden force that paralyzes but also configures us as humans or as non-humans.

What has been sealed in the past in the name of "civilization" and "progress", there is also everything that has been relegated to the shadows, to preserve an idea of a person and human being. All this has been relegated to the closet, to the room where old things are kept, to the junk room.

The concept of Human

Hence, civilization and human nature, the human that has been considered characteristic of Western culture, is constantly questioned when confronted with the monstrous. We have to start with something. What do we talk about when it comes to

⁸ Historicism, contrary to Benjamin's analysis of history against the grain, poses an "eternal" static image of the past, the historical materialist instead posits a moving experience with the past that is unique.

human nature? What are the characteristics of humans? What are the characteristics proposed by the humanist movement that inaugurates man as the center of all things. How is the human configured from this perspective?

Among the main characteristics of humanism, I will highlight the following: Eurocentrism, or, anthropocentrism to be more specific, human intelligence based on reason, and the idea of a free being.

European Anthropocentrism consisted of the idea of the human being as the center of all things, in opposition to the theological thought of the Middle Ages in which God was the center of life. Human intelligence was held as the supreme value to justify existence--the idea of a free being with free will who, through reason, was capable of making his own decisions, as opposed to obeying absolute authority, or a Divine authority.

It was believed that there was a universal morality governing man, deducing that it could be said that all people are intrinsically free and equal, but based on reality this is not true for everyone.⁹

For Rousseau or Kant, the universal law of reason guided humans toward the total emancipation of any type of tyranny. This idea, as a project of political emancipation, materialized in the constitution of Human Rights.¹⁰

Humanism attributes a universal essence to humanity, privileging it over other forms of existence. This vision of the world was possible due to the incorporation of new knowledge and understanding from reason to supposedly combat ignorance and superstition. Why does privilege follow from essentialism? Perhaps this is the argument by which a humanity centered on "reason" grants a privilege to an essence, from my point of view humans are beings in permanent change and what we value and privilege also changes according to the circumstances that arise around us.

However, the idea of God and the divine as a non-specific principle or being that gives rise to the world and is a source of life did not cease to exist at the age of Illuminism developed in Europe during the 18th century,¹¹ nor did the ignorance to understand that other types of knowledge of the world are not based on reason.¹² The figure of the creator God was still relevant since he played a fundamental role in the conception of the universe. Although the separation of the church from the state was promoted. In this way, the idea of God remains latent in the Humanist vision and manifests itself, for example, in what we know as the golden ratio¹³ for possessing

⁹ This way of thinking ignores that there are differences between cultures and individuals. However, from my point of view, even today this ideal of the rational human being continues to prevail as the most valuable.

¹⁰ For Marx, "humanity" is an unreal abstraction: because one's rights are abstract, the justice and equality they protect are also abstract, allowing for extreme inequalities in reality.

¹¹ Proof of it is the divine proportion represented by numbers and the idea of the Divine in musical notes. Hence, music linked to science

<https://sites.google.com/site/esteticadephi/proporcion-aurea/proporciones-armonicas/armonias-musicales>

¹² Intuition for example, or knowledge through emotions, to name a few.

¹³ The fascination that human beings have felt for many centuries with the golden ratio is due in large part to its many interesting properties, among which harmony, regeneration, balance stand out among others.

Luca Pacioli, to whom the divine character is attributed to the golden ratio, relates the qualities of the golden ratio to divinity. The Renaissance is open. The notion of divinity is a kind of bond that extends to Pythagoras and his religious school where ἀριθμός (arithmós, mathematics) prevails, passing through Plato who linked numbers with Δημιουργός (Dēmiurgós), shaper of the world. Franco Ferrari says that in the Platonic vision "...the demiurge fulfills the role of

characteristics that are attributed to the divine, which was and continues to be a tool for humanity.

Also, it is in this time of transition between the Middle Ages and the modern age that the conditions given allowed the emergence of modern science that sees the light within the Renaissance movement linked to Humanism. With the division of knowledge, the figure of the artist/scientist, or the scientist/artist, arises. Leonardo Da Vinci¹⁴ is the best-known example of this. His work *The Vitruvian Man*, or study of the ideal proportions of the human body, is a classic work that shows Da Vinci's understanding of the ideal proportions of the human male body. The idea of a type of physical body that was believed to be of perfect proportions—linked to the body of the man, and not in this case of the woman) raises links to the Divine. The golden ratio would become a basic principle of beauty because it is believed that an ideal spirit permeates all things. Before humanism, God was the measure of all things, and in humanism, man becomes the center and measure of all things. However, with the idea that man is made in the likeness of God, then we return to God.

From this vision of the world, there is talk of a single type of human and from this other living beings are valued, from a Eurocentric anthropocentrism with a static vision of the nature of the human.

When rationalism was inaugurated with humanism and when it intersected with the revolutions in Europe—the Industrial Revolution among them— it gave rise to mass production. It is the moment in which technological wonders appear, but also a series of inequalities and violence against living beings, who were considered subhuman or non/human and often relegated to work in factories. We know that human rights, in a framework of illegality of beings that are not considered human, subhumans, marginal beings, migrants at borders, to name a few examples, human dignity and

self-realization are things that do not exist, what exists is the law of the "bravest" and the priority is to survive.

The subhuman, non/human, does not exist. So, in this scenario, only those considered human have the right to demand their Human Rights, those not considered human are confined to the shadows.

Then, the anti-humanists take the floor. Nietzsche will declare the death of God on the one hand, and, later, Foucault declares the death of Man. On the other hand, antihumanism as a line of thought questioning Humanism in its assumptions brings to light the violence and atrocities committed in the name of reason. It questions both logocentrism and anthropocentrism, and severely criticizes Human Rights¹⁵ and the failure of humanism to fulfill his emancipatory ideal.

efficient cause while the world of ideas constitutes the paradigmatic cause of the cosmos." the Platonic notion of the demiurge as a prefiguration of God and the religious vision of Luca Pacioli have the divine as their backbone.

¹⁴ Leonardo da Vinci (Leonardo di ser Piero da Vinci) (Vinci, April 15, 1452-Amboise, May 2, 1519) was a Florentine polymath of the Italian Renaissance. He was at the same time a painter, anatomist, architect, paleontologist, botanist, writer, sculptor, philosopher, engineer, inventor, musician, poet and urban planner. Wikipedia: https://es.wikipedia.org/wiki/Leonardo_da_Vinci

¹⁵ In his *Genealogy of Morality*, he argues that human rights exist as a means for the weak to collectively limit the strong. In this view, these rights do not facilitate life emancipation, but rather deny it. For Friedrich Nietzsche, humanism was nothing more than a secular version of theism.

Thus, from a new decentered view of man (but no longer towards God), one thinks not only of "a single human nature," but of the diversity of the human, of human becoming from the understanding of reality as a process, structure, system, relationships, transformation, intensity, difference, and subconscious, to mention just a few.

Human/Transhuman/Posthuman

Antihumanism is another way of thinking about humanity and the posthuman human critical theory has emerged questioning modern science, cutting-edge technology and philosophy.

On the one hand, we can understand Posthumanism from the lines of thought that aspire to overcome Humanism from the classical Renaissance idea and update these conceptions after the second half of the 20th century. It is also understood by Posthumanism as the reflection that comes after postmodern, postcolonial, gender, and race theory.

It is then that Posthumanism is not about understanding what the human being is in essence, as classical humanism proposes, but about reflecting on what the human wants to become, and what he can become. It is also about approaching a reflection from a non-binary perspective of what is conceived as human.

In this way, with the possible emergence of a new human prototype, a period of reflection on the promises of technology opens again.¹⁶

Posthumanism thus poses, on the one hand, a technological posthumanism, and another non-technological, and we can think then on Posthumanism in plural: Critical Posthumanism, Cultural Posthumanism and Philosophical Posthumanism, among other Posthumanism(s) linked by the deconstruction of the Human (Fernando 2017)¹⁷ Within the critical reflection that technological Posthumanism addresses, issues related to Transhumanism are contemplated (which is a political movement, from my point of view; rather practical, and that goes hand in hand with scientific and technological advances, that they are not accessible to ordinary people¹⁸).

This is the version of transhumanism that is described by Natasha Vita-More: *"Transhumanism is a class of philosophies of life that seek the continuation and acceleration of the evolution of intelligent life beyond its currently human form and human limitations by means of science and technology, guided by life-promoting principles and values"* (More 2013: 3). In other words: the human in transition who seeks to redesign and improve themselves in order to have a longer and healthier life through biomedical interventions, artificial intelligence, nanomedicine, genetic engineering, among others, in addition to demanding their right to preserve autonomy

¹⁶ Here, it is worth remembering the reflection that Heidegger would make on the subject of technology and its dangers at the time, and that it is still pertinent to take into account Heidegger is considered among the most important philosophers of the 20th century for his theoretical contribution about being and existence.

¹⁷ Francesca Fernando explains to us in a very didactic way what is meant by posthumanism in her master class published online in the Latin American magazine of posthumanism

¹⁸ I'm among this people

.But this human enhancement its not accessible to all the people, so this continuation and acceleration of “evolution”¹⁹ is only for a few.

Human/inhuman/unhuman/subhuman

The concept of human that can be understood today, starting from the reflections of both antihumanism and posthumanism, is not a single essence, but a diversity of people in constant transformation. However, we know that throughout the history of the West, and of humanistic cultures, not all beings that are now included as humans have been considered as such. Not all people have been seen as morally fit for autonomy and the practice of "free will".

Such is the case of women, who at times have been considered as "inferior" or as "incomplete man" As in the ancient Greek culture for example, the woman was considered as inferior. So, she was under the permanent guardianship of a man: father, brother or husband,²⁰ or also the case of people with a skin color different than white, of a different ethnicity from Caucasian, or people with cultural practices that have been classified as "inferior" or "primitive."²¹

Derrida with his theory of deconstruction shows how this violence has been exercised since the deconstruction of logocentrism (Derrida 2008: 111). For example, in his deconstructive reading on the animal issue.²² He points out that anthropocentric logic leads us to all kinds of exclusions; it is thought that if living beings are not human, they can therefore be put into a single category. Hence, the violence that such a conceptual simplification means is, for purposes of understanding other sentient beings, an absurdity that has led man to exercise the violence that exists in the industrial treatment of meat for consumption, leading animals to the slaughterhouse and to be treated from the beginning of their lives, until their death, with absolute cruelty.

The case of experiments using animals in scientific laboratories is no exception. However, the cruelty that is exercised in the name of scientific advances seems to have a certain touch of indifference that scientific practice itself demands.²³ The immediate consequence of putting these living beings in the category of “animals” is that they become objects for scientific and industrial use, leaving aside their sentient natures.

Violence and cruelty are also exercised between people that we assume to be human, such as the case of sadomasochistic practices that we assume are consensual between humans and humans, or in the case of people who have been classified as psychopaths. But there is always a subject-object relationship in these cases. If for some individuals, apparently cruelty is pleasurable,²⁴ For others indifference is what characterizes it. How can we understand the in/unhuman at this point?

¹⁹ Evolution, here is an obscure term, since it pursues a teleological end, where it is not clear who will benefit from these technological improvements.

²⁰ Michel Foucault in his History of Sexuality describes how women were not considered as human, for example in Greek ancient culture.

²¹ We can find both in philosophy and the emergence of anthropology various examples of this.

²² Derrida argues that it is violent to put so much diversity of living beings in a single category such as animals.

²³ My testimony as a student of Experimental Biology

²⁴ In sadomasochistic practices that we assume are consensual, or in the case of people who have been classified as psychopaths.

The human then can be understood today, starting from the reflections of both antihumanism and posthumanism, not as a single essence, but as a diversity of humans in constant transformation.

We know then, that the borders between the human and the non-human have been mobile throughout history, but not without suffering, bloodshed, and injustices inherent to a revolution both in ways of thinking and in customs. Violence is something common that accompanies great changes where both the inhuman and the unhuman are revealed.

How can we think of the *non-human*, the *in/unhuman*, in such a way that we can have an understanding of the limits of the *human*?

What does it mean to be *unhuman*? What is supposed constitutes us as human beings in its broadest definition, is its construction of culture and civilization. So, what then what does it mean to be civilized? On one hand, the relationship of the human “the civilized” in opposition with such a kind of “other” “the uncivilized”, is being redefined according to times and customs. And on the other hand, the relationship with “other” living beings in their animal nature is a paradox that denies the animal part of the human and annihilates it.

Everything that has had to be discarded, expelled, and vomited because it is intolerable for a civilized being is everything that defines an unhuman. The animal part of a human being has to be tamed, sublimated, or hidden in the dark.

What does it mean to be *inhuman*? An excess of civilization eliminates emotions and over-values reason. Paradoxically, an excess of rationality leads humanity to use their intelligence for destruction (proof of this are wars and the use of cutting-edge technology for warlike purposes).

What does it mean to be *subhuman*? is that being that is exploited by mass production and it is disposable, replaceable. Mass production makes *trash humans*.

The *inhuman*, in contrast, is a chimera—half human/half animal, and is beyond morality. Most of the time he is proud of who he is (but sometimes we don’t know if the inhuman being hates itself).

Then, the *Unhuman* is the monster that no one wants to be, the one that everyone rejects, the amorphous, the waste, it is the chimera, and it is the corpse as well. It embraces, too, the superhuman, the supernatural, the demonic, and the subhuman; the supposedly disjunctive animal, vegetable, and mineral kingdoms; the realms of artifice, technology, and fantasy.²⁵

If the unhuman does not necessarily mean the inhuman, in the sense of conspicuous or extraordinary cruelty, then what is inhuman is what is forbidden; it is a perversion, but also the monster in another sense, the one that pushes the limits beyond the monster that many who have been alienated by civilization secretly admire.

Hence, Unhuman and inhuman remain in this imaginary civilization marginalized from the rest, hidden in the dark, in the collective subconscious. They require the oblivion of consciousness, absent from the light but always looking for the

²⁵ In his book "Unhuman Culture" Cotton talks about artistic practices related to the unhuman

crack that makes them visible from time to time, to make room for the “other” world. It is then that the Unhuman, the monstrous, can be understood as being from the order of the abject.

Where are the monsters hiding?

Kristeva tells us about the abject in her “Powers of Horror”²⁶ relying on both Freudian and Lacanian theories, that abjection is of primary order in the constitution of identity. It is everything that escapes significance in the symbolic order, and the abject is precisely where the meaning cracks. When Kristeva speaks of abjection, she refers to what is expelled from a human reaction to horror that causes a breakdown of meaning, where there is a loss of distinction between subject and object, or between self and other. In that sense, the abject has to be radically excluded to preserve identity, since the danger lies, as Kristeva explains, in that the abject attracts where the meaning collapses.

Kristeva refers to the abject moment when a separation is established between what is considered human and animal, between what is considered culture and what precedes it. Vomiting then is the act of expulsion of what threatens the identity. The abject is neither subject nor object, it is what has not yet entered the symbolic order.²⁷

The abject, Kristeva tells us, marks a first repression that precedes the subject's relationship with its object of desire and its representation, long before the opposition between conscious and unconscious is established.²⁸ Abjection preserves with violence what exists before a body separates from another body to be (Powers 10, in “Powers of Horror”) thus, abjection preserves a body in its integrity. What exists before the instant in which one body separates from another is what I call here the monstrous.

Hence, we can say that the monstrous object belongs to the order of the abject. The monstrous is the shadow that humanity projects, what has to be repressed for the human to be. It elicits a pre-lingual response, such as instinctive horror and rejection, and causes the urge to vomit at something intolerable or incomprehensible. The dead, the corpse as an incomprehensible limit²⁹, war crimes, cruelty towards other living beings; but also other sexualities, other sensitivities, other cultures. Continuing with Kristeva, the abject is the threat of what shakes identity, what destabilizes a system, what disturbs an established order. It is what does not respect limits, laws, or rules.³⁰

²⁶ The work of Kristeva in this book, is an extensive treatise on the subject of abjection, in which Kristeva draws on the theories of Sigmund Freud and Jacques Lacan to examine horror, marginalization, castration, the phallic signifier, the “I/Not I” dichotomy, the Oedipal complex, exile, among other concepts.

²⁷ Kristeva's understanding of the “abject” provides a helpful term to contrast to Lacan's *objet petit a* (or the “object - cause of desire”). Whereas the *objet petit a* allows a subject to coordinate his or her desires, thus allowing the symbolic order of meaning and intersubjective community to persist, the abject “is radically excluded” and, as Kristeva explains, “draws toward the place where meaning collapses” (Powers 2). It is neither object nor subject; the abject is situated, rather, at a place before we entered into the symbolic order....

²⁸ The abject marks what Kristeva terms a “primal repression,” one that precedes the establishment of the subject's relation to its objects of desire and of representation, before even the establishment of the opposition between consciousness and the unconscious.

²⁹ Kristeva is quite careful to differentiate knowledge of death or the meaning of death: “The corpse, seen without God and outside of science, is the utmost of abjection. It is death infecting life. Abject” (Powers 4).

³⁰ The abject thus at once represents the threat that meaning is breaking down and constitutes our reaction to such a breakdown: a reestablishment of our “primal repression.” The abject has to do with “what disturbs identity, system,

Thus, the *Abject* in the first instance represents the threat (the rupture with the meaning), but at the same time reestablishes an order, identity, and law; it stabilizes the systems, with the re-establishment of the repression of that which threatens.

Could we also think of the *Abject* as a possible catalyst for transformations? By destabilizing the limits of one body and another body and thereby re-establishing another order, another identity, a new system?

The monstrous can also be something very subjective. For certain people something may be intolerable, others may feel fascination³¹. So, we can ask if this emergence of the monstrous can be associated with changes to access Other Worlds.

In this sense, Kristeva also associates the abject with *la joinissance* and the sublime.³² The monsters hide in the subconscious and appear, from time to time, not only in the perversions of humanity but also in Art and are sublimated in poetic catharsis.

Examples of this in the arts that are quite well known, which we could call transhumanist art, can be found in the work of Stelarc, who works with robotic "chimeras" and Orlan, included within the Unhuman culture by Otto; who has modified his body in ways inspired by the aesthetic canons of other cultures, through aesthetic surgeries.

What is repressed inevitably emerges as a disease³³. That is to say, what is repressed always remains latent, the monstrous always lurks. So, from time to time, the monster appears and allows itself to be glimpsed through symptoms: social inequality, climate change, social illnesses, mental illnesses in the population, unjustified acceleration of production, addiction to social networks, etc.

The Monster and Moustrosity

The monster has historically symbolized what does not fit. It represents the threat of difference –what challenges identity, gender, species. But, as J.Derrida shows, the monster can also be the figure of what we don't yet understand. It is not simply an error, but a form of otherness that announces change.

The notion of the Derridian monstrous, understood as that which cannot be figured or represented. Representation will not be a matter of presence, but rather of "invisibility," of the invisible event that nevertheless opens up an expansive space in which the mystery of representation itself exist in/on the torsión of the Mobius surface.

The monstrous, in this sense, and although un-figurable, would be precisely the other to whom acceptance is denied.

Jacques Derrida argues that "what is to come" is not just a future that will arrive, but an opening to what cannot yet be named. The monster is this figure: something

order. What does not respect borders, positions, rules" (Powers 4) and, so, can also include crimes like Auschwitz. Such crimes are abject precisely because they draw *attention to the "fragility of the law"* (Powers 4).

³¹ Kristeva also associates the abject with *jouissance*: the aesthetic experience of the abject (instead, of a poetic catharsis) is "*an impure process that protects from the abject only by dint of being immersed in it*" (Powers 29).

The abject for Kristeva is, therefore, closely tied both to religion and to art.

³² The transcendent or sublime, for Kristeva, is really our effort to cover over the breakdowns (and subsequent reassertion of boundaries) associated with the abject. Art, and specially, literature is the privileged space for both the sublime and abject

³³ As Freud points out about the unconscious and in his essay "The discomfort in culture"

new that exceeds our current language and categories. It unsettles us precisely because we don't know how to integrate it. But for that reason, it holds the possibility of another world –another way of being.

Derrida's reference to "monstrosity" relates to his idea that the future is unpredictable and always arrives as a "monstrosity" because it defies our categories and expectations.

The central idea is that we cannot fully plan or anticipate the future. *"The future can only be anticipated in the form of absolute danger. It completely breaks with established normality and, therefore, cannot be announced or presented except in the form of monstrosity"* (Derrida, 2008) When it arrives, it appears as something beyond our understanding and disarms us, forcing us to live in its uncertainty.

Where will all the monsters go?

Thus, abjection is important to understand the way in which the human is constituted from what it hides, by discarding and expelling it, thereby constituting what is a limit between what is considered human and what is considered inhuman. However, from this perspective, we continue in a human/inhuman binary reflection, hence, it is essential to understand the human in a constant process of change, the object that constitutes it, making it visible, and dialoguing with it in a constant negotiation of limits.

Here, I take a few steps to outline a horizon through which the Post/Transhuman can be analyzed from an understanding of the monstrous (un/inhuman), opening a series of questions to develop in future texts.

First of all, on the question of the human: at what point can a living being be considered human, from which a transformation could take place towards becoming a Post/Transhuman? And at what point does a human stop being human, to become Post/Transhuman?

Let's assume then, from this point of view, that the human is a being in constant transformation and can decide using free will³⁴ what type of living being he wants to transform into. What prototypes of people are being developed? What kind of bodies, forms, or systems are possible from these transformations?

The constant questioning of what seems "the natural course of things", such as what transhumanism places on the implementation of improvements and the evolution of the human in transhuman, is a necessary way to test the presuppositions and values that come into play. As Foucault points out, we must question what is passed off as "normal" in this case as "the nature of things".

On the other hand, the ideal of beauty proposed by humanism is not the only one that exists today.

However, within the Transhumanist movement these ideals of beauty could be the common ones (just look at the 3D models that can be downloaded for free on the Internet and that have characteristics of a Caucasian man). Alternatively, in the arts, other discourses are opposed to this ideal of beauty, allowing us to propose the idea of abject art, leading to the thought that, at present, it's really not necessary to appeal

³⁴ Although free will was questioned so much since the subconscious is the one that decides and does not reason until the microbiome has to do with our decision-making capacity and the same neurosciences question free will.

to mathematics and the golden ratio to verify that something can be considered beautiful, and to what degree.

If we take it for granted that we are talking about a vision of the human proposed by classical Humanism as the one that is in transition, we start from certain characteristics and standards of beauty imposed by the classical humanist vision within Western culture. What then is the transition that is emerging in a transhuman? What are the changes concerning Eurocentric humans? What parameters of beauty and proportions are we talking about when we say that we can redesign our body according to our choice? What values, beliefs, and desires are at stake?

There is indeed talk of free will and the ability to decide on one's own body. However, this choice is often directed by the unconscious and the ideal of Western beauty and its values.. What does it mean to be improved from these parameters?

A proposal for better future scenarios, as Benjamin proposed in his "Theses on the Philosophy of History", could emerge by recognizing the various histories obturated by Western culture, and in the emancipation of the West by paying off its debt with those other cultures. Also, by knowing how to face and reconcile with the hidden, with everything that is relegated to the shadows to put what is considered human in the foreground.

The point here is that there is still no clear idea of what separates the human from the non/human, in/unhuman, and what rights other sentient beings should have, nor what it means to be a valued life form and live in a dignified manner³⁵.

One can speculate about the future types of people, bodies, forms, or systems among which we will be able to exist, but one cannot escape debt and the hidden because they always come to light as symptoms.

With Transhumanism and the possibility of a longer life, there is also speculation about the possibility of a life that does not contemplate death as one of its possibilities. So, what kind of being could emerge as a transhuman that lives eternally? From what values would this living being be governed?³⁶ What would be the predominant values? Why have a longer life based on technology when more technology seems to cause more anxiety and mental illness?³⁷

On the other hand, how is the notion of "healthy" defined by transhumanism? The following follows: how to ensure a society of mentally and physically healthy beings when it is in constant transformation.³⁸

³⁵ Posthumanism broadens the scope of what it means to be a valued life form and to be treated as such (in contrast to certain life forms that are viewed as inferior and are taken advantage of or killed); "It calls for a more inclusive definition of life, and a greater moral and ethical response, and greater responsibility, towards non-human life forms in the age of confusion and intermingling of species. ... It questions the hierarchical ordering, and later the exploitation and even the eradication, of the forms of life"

³⁶ Heidegger posits "being for death" as the essence of *DasEin's* being in his reflection in his book "*Being and Time*" It is a fact that not as the being for death that we are today's humans.

³⁷ For example, if it happens connected to the Internet, especially in the so-called social networks where popular content is not exactly what exalts the human being? The clearest example is that people live connected to the Internet where their apparent happiness depends on the number of likes they get, regardless of the content, it is well known that cultural or intellectual, or spiritual content is not the most popular.

³⁸ One of the ways is the acceptance that there are intolerable and monstrous things that perhaps for those who work on scientific and technological advances and for who work on these fascinating transformations, due to their optimism and confidence in scientific knowledge, exist as a blind spot, without which science could not advance in its purposes. No,

Transhumanism, from my point of view, is led by an uncritical enthusiasm and a blind faith in the "objectivity"³⁹ of science and cutting-edge technology, assuming that "free will" exists and can be exercised by all persons (questioned both by philosophy and by neurosciences, as for psychology and even for the existence of the microbiome "that leads our decisions") I suspect that transhumanism takes for granted that all people are born free and equal and that they can be rationally autonomous when that is in reality very far from the reality of many. If so, then this idealism must be questioned, since it closes the range of possibilities for better future scenarios. We cannot forget the condition of humans as sentient beings in relation to their environment and to other forms of life, and that in addition to being individuals, they are also social and historical beings.

Is it in the self-observation (as if it were the daily cleaning and maintenance of a house) that humanity creates of itself, in the rigorous and constant questioning of what seems to be "the normal course of things" and in the recognition of one's own shadow, one of the ways by which posthumanism and the transhumanist movement could build better scenarios for living beings?

Recognizing the atrocities that humanity has committed in favor of the "progress of humanity" is recognizing how monstrous it is. Dealing with this is the task to enable it to transcend. Hence, the Future is in the past and also in the things that have been left hidden in the dark.

Many things that have been left in the "box of chess pieces" by Western culture and Eurocentric Humanism consist of a meticulous work of self-observation to know how to deal with what, on the one hand, has remained as debt towards cultures obturated in favor of the emergence of Western culture, and on the other hand, the monstrous hidden in the shadows. In the end, they pass the cost on to society by emerging as symptoms.

So, to transcend their condition in a dignified manner and to be able to lay the foundations for possibly better future scenarios, humans must take charge of the "forgotten" part. The human of the future, as a part of, and also indebted to, Western culture, will only be able to transcend as post-transhuman by emancipating himself from debt and through the recognition, integration, and transformation in our favor of the monstrous. Thinking of the human not as an opposition human/inhuman, but as a constant transformation through negotiating the limits that constitute it, dialoguing with the monstrosity that constitutes us.

It is then that to be a Transhuman ("to have a longer life healthy and happy"⁴⁰) is not only a matter of having technological improvements on our body, it is also, from my point of view, maintaining a constant and open dialogue and resignification with our here and now as well as with the past of humanity.

however, it is not a justification for society not to take charge of this, hence the need for a critical posthumanism from which one can reflect and propose on these issues. That is to say, We know that by the very structure of science, it is incapable of thinking by itself, that is to say, reflecting on its own doing in the sense that Heidegger points out.

³⁹ Due to its structure, science does not think, Heidegger would say in his reflection on modern scientific work, was *is das Denken*"

⁴⁰ While being healthy seems like a fairly straightforward term, being happy is instead a very subjective matter.

The Monster as a promise

Hence *the monster as a promise* is already a human in transformation: trans, cybernetic, posthuman, enhanced by technology or mutation. It no longer conforms to the old norm. That's why it is seen as monstrous. But if we follow Derrida, this body also anticipates new forms of life, community, and ethics.

To embrace the monstrous is not to embrace chaos. It means opening ourselves to the unknown. Rethinking humanity through the Mysterious Strip Posthuman Terrain means to think –through the plurality of possible scenarios that merge from the “contradictions”. From this point of view the monster is a promise, not just a threat. It is the possibility of reimagining what it means to be the Posthuman of the human from the threshold of a *Posthuman Being*.

References

1. Althusser, L., 1974. La filosofía como arma de la Revolución. Editorial Cuadernos de Pasado y Presente, México D. F.
2. Arteaga, A., 2004. Aspectos estéticos de la divina proporción. Tesis doctoral, Universidad Complutense de Madrid, España.
3. Benjamin, W., 1971. Tesis sobre filosofía de la historia. Angelous Novus. Barcelona: Edhasa.
4. Derrida, Jacques; Sussana, Gad y Nouss, Alexis (2006). Decir el acontecimiento, ¿es posible? Madrid: Arena Libros.
5. Foucault, M., 2007. Historia de la sexualidad 1. La voluntad de saber (31a. edición). México: Siglo XXI. México
7. Hemenway, P. 2008. El Código Secreto. La Misteriosa Fórmula Que Rige El Arte, La Naturaleza y La Ciencia. Colonia: Evergreen.
8. Jung, C. G., 1928. El Yo y el Inconsciente. Paidós, Biblioteca Jung
9. Jung, C. G., 1954. Arquetipos e inconsciente colectivo Paidós, Biblioteca Carl G. Jung
10. Kuhn, T. 2005. La estructura de las revoluciones científicas. México: Fondo de Cultura Económica. Kristeva, J., 1988. Poderes de la perversión. Ensayo sobre Louis-Ferdinand Celine. México: Siglo XXI
11. Lacan, Jacques. (1961–1962). Seminario, Libro 9: La identificación. Editorial Paidós Lacan, Jacques. (1962–1963) Seminario, Libro 10: La angustia. Editorial Paidós Lacan, Jacques. Escritos II. Siglo XXI, 2005.
12. Luca, P. et.al, 2008. La divina proporción Madrid : Akal Editorial
13. Majidi, Sepideh, posthuman Terrains, 2022. Posthuman art Network. Foreign Objekt Nietzsche, F. 2003. La genealogía de la moral. España: Tecnos.
14. More, M. 2013. The philosophy of transhumanism. In M. More & N. Vita-More (Eds.), The Transhumanist Reader: Classical and contemporary essays on the science, technology, and philosophy of the human future (pp. 3–17). New York: Wiley.

Online References

1. Majidi Sepideh, “Posthuman Terrains”: Posthuman Art Network, Apr 29, 2022, <https://www.posthumanart.com/post/posthuman-terrains-sepideh-majidi>
<https://www.posthumanart.com/posthuman-terrains>
<https://www.posthumanart.com/post/posthuman-terrains-sepideh-majidi>
2. Magenta 2022, “Odioica: Transhumanism as an involution”, Posthuman Art Network, May 5, 2022 www.posthumanart.com/post/odioica-transhumanism-as-an-involution-by-magenta-1
3. Magenta 2022, “Unhuman: The twist in the surface”, Posthuman Art Network, Foreign Objekt,
4. Posthuman Agency Lab, Dec 6, 2022 <https://www.posthumanart.com/post/unhuman>
<https://www.posthumanart.com/post/unhuman-the-twist-in-the-surface-by-magenta>

5. https://redaprenderycambiar.com.ar/derrida/textos/levi_strauss.htm
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=FERuqxO4TQs>, Last access: 09 March, 2023.
6. Feinmann, José Pablo, 2009. "Filosofía Aquí & Ahora", 2ª Temporada: ¿Por qué Heidegger es el filósofo más importante del Siglo XX? Last access: Jan 05 2023.
7. Ferrando, F.2017. Masterclass, New York University (NYU) – Red Global de Posthumanismo : https://posthumanismo.org/masterclass-sobre-posthumanismo-filosofico-con-francesca-ferrando/?play_list=169c921&video=cf5fe78 ,
8. Study Group with Natasha Vita More: Transhumanist Aesthetics: Exponential Systems for Life, Posthuman Art Network, Foreign Objekt, 11 jul 2022 <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Ou9GFv20xHA>
9. Study Group with Alireza Taheri, "Psychoanalytic Topology" Posthuman Art Network, Foreign Objekt, 29 may 2022 <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=INe6tV4HEXI&t=123s>
10. Davis Roden ,Study Group with David Roden: "Posthuman Dialectics: The Antinomy of Embodiment and Abstraction", Posthuman Art Network, Foreign Objekt, 5 jul 2022 <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=sOnVKR4s5vU&t=5710s>